

More than one way to catch a TALE: Comparing recognition mechanisms of tomato
resistance protein Bs4 and rice resistance protein Xo1

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Abstract

Plant-pathogenic bacteria in the *Xanthomonas* genus employ a host of effector proteins known as transcription activator-like effectors (TALEs) which aid in virulence through nuclear localization and activation of host susceptibility genes. There are few nuclear-binding leucine-rich repeat proteins (NLRs) known to target TALEs and confer resistance to infection by *Xanthomonas*. The NLRs Xo1 in rice and Bs4 in tomato confer resistance to *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* (Xoc) and *X. campestris* pv. *vesicatoria* (Xcv) (respectively) by recognizing TALEs with diverse nuclear binding specificity. Certain strains of Xoc contain TALE-like proteins with truncations in the N- and C-termini (truncTALEs) that were found to interfere with Xo1-mediated resistance. Here I found that despite their similarity in function, there are key differences in Xo1 and Bs4 recognition of TALEs based on structural requirements of the target TALE that suggest convergent evolution of these two NLRs. While Xo1 requires the C-terminus and 3.5 central repeats of a TALE for recognition, the N-terminus and 2.5 repeats are sufficient for Bs4 recognition. Additionally, TALE spine mutations in the 31-32nd amino acid of each central repeat have been observed to interfere with Xo1 resistance do not affect Bs4 resistance, and nuclear exclusion of Bs4 does not interfere with resistance. Bs4 is neither triggered nor suppressed by truncTALEs.

Introduction

Bacteria in the *Xanthomonas* genus infect over 400 plant species, causing significant damage to economically important crops including rice and tomato (Timilsina et al. 2020). A class of protein virulence factors called transcription activator-like effectors (TALEs) are widespread in *Xanthomonas* (Timilsina et al. 2020, Boch et al. 2014). TALEs are a group of bacterial virulence factors present in *Xanthomonas* species as well as certain *Ralstonia* species, a group of bacteria which causes devastating wilt on Solanaceous plants (Li et al. 2013). These plant pathogens inject TALEs into plant cells, where they bind specifically to host gene promoters and act as transcription factors, enhancing transcription of host genes to aid bacterial growth and dispersal (Boch et al. 2014). TALE binding specificity is determined by a sequence of repeat units in the central repeat region (CRR), where each unit interacts with a specific DNA nucleotide (Bogdanove et al. 2010). Recognition of TALEs by the plant is often mediated by an intermediate executor (E) gene, which activates downstream signaling and resistance when bound by a TALE (Zhang et al. 2015). This resistance mechanism is sensitive to minor perturbations in the TALE binding site of host plant DNA, and often depends on the upregulation of the E gene by a single TALE with a specific CRR (Zhang et al. 2015). Therefore, E gene-based resistance does not have the ability to recognize diverse TALEs from multiple bacterial strains. An alternative method of resistance mediated by the tomato resistance (R) protein Bs4 and the rice R protein Xo1 facilitates broad recognition of TALEs regardless of DNA binding specificity, providing resistance to *Xanthomonas* strains that express diverse TALEs (Triplett et al. 2016, Schornack et al. 2004). Understanding the recognition ability of these R proteins has significant implications for engineering resistance to *Xanthomonas* and other plant pathogens that carry TALEs.

The structure of a TALE (**Figure 1a**) can be divided into the N-terminal region, the CRR, and the C-terminal region. The N-terminal region contains the Type III secretion signal (T3S), and the C-terminal region contains nuclear localization signals (NLS) and an acidic activation domain (AD) (Boch et al. 2014). The CRR is composed of several 33-34 amino acid repeats and a single 20 amino acid truncated (0.5) repeat. The repeats are polymorphic at the 12-13 amino acid position (the repeat-variable diresidue or RVD) (Bogdanove et al. 2010). This polymorphism defines the DNA

binding specificity of each TALE, with sequences of RVDs associating directly with sequences of nucleotides in the host promoter (Boch et al. 2009). This leads to a large amount of diversity within TALE CRRs, with varying RVDs and repeat lengths, while the N- and C- terminal regions are more highly conserved.

Figure 1. Key domains of a TALE and a truncated TALE (truncTALE). (a) The N-terminus and C-terminus of a TALE contain the T3S, the NLS, and the AD. The TALE CRR contains variable numbers of repeat units with polymorphic RVDs encoding which nucleotide the repeat binds. The CRR ends with a 20 amino acid (0.5) shortened repeat. (b) TruncTALEs contain deletions in the N- and C-terminal regions, retaining the T3S and one NLS but missing the AD.

Typically, the plant immune response is a multi-layered process that includes plant recognition of secreted bacterial effectors or effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (Jones and Dangl 2006, Ngou et al. 2022). ETI is mediated by a class of plant proteins called nucleotide-binding leucine-rich repeat receptors (NLRs) (Ngou et al. 2022, Contreras et al. 2023). NLRs are typically composed of the C-terminal leucine-rich repeat (LRR), the central nucleotide-binding and oligomerization domain (NOD), and a variable N-terminal domain involved in signaling. This domain is categorized into one of four main types, including the RESISTANCE TO POWDERY MILDEW 8 (RPM8)-type and G10-type coiled-coil (CC_{G10}). Of relevance to this study are the coiled-coil (CC) and toll/interleukin-1 receptor (TIR) NLR types (Contreras et al. 2023). The traditional model of gene-for-gene resistance involves a plant NLR specialized to detect a pathogen effector, which upon effector detection, triggers a signaling cascade that leads to hypersensitive response (HR), a form of programmed cell death, and resistance (Biezen et al. 1998).

The NLRs Bs4 and Xo1 confer resistance to two *Xanthomonas* species of interest: *X. campestris* pv. *vesicatoria* (Xcv), which causes bacterial spot of tomato and pepper, and *X. oryzae* pv. *oryzicola* (Xoc), which causes bacterial leaf streak on rice. Both pathogens are commercially important, with Xcv causing up to 66% yield loss in tomato and Xoc causing up to 32% loss of rice. Both express a variety of TALEs with diverse DNA binding specificity (Adhikari et al. 2020, Jiang et al. 2020). Typically, for NLRs which detect effectors through direct binding, one NLR detects one pathogen virulence factor and its alleles (Contreras et al. 2023). Both Xo1 and Bs4 NLRs can detect TALEs regardless of DNA binding specificity, a mechanism which is unique among resistance genes against TALE-carrying *Xanthomonas* (Schornack et al. 2003, Triplett et al. 2016).

Xo1 is a rice CC-NLR found in the rice cultivar ‘Carolina Gold’ that confers resistance to multiple African strains of Xoc, recognizing TALEs such as TalC and Tal5 from *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* and Tal1c, Tal2a, and Tal8 from Xoc (**Figure 2a, 2c**) (Triplett et al. 2016). TALE recognition by Xo1 is independent of the CRR composition and requires a minimum of 3.5 central repeats but not the AD (Triplett et al. 2016). This implies that Xo1 does not require transcriptional activation to trigger resistance. Certain non-DNA-binding truncated TALEs (truncTALEs or iTALEs) with major deletions in the N- and C-terminal regions (**Figure 1b**) are naturally found in Asian strains of Xoc, to which Xo1 does not confer resistance (Read et al. 2016, Ji et al. 2016). TruncTALEs have been found to suppress Xo1 resistance when expressed by Xoc (Read 2016). TruncTALEs also suppress the Xo1 allele Xa1, which also confers broad-spectrum resistance to *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Ji et al. 2016).

Bs4 is a tomato TIR-NLR that recognizes TALEs from Xcv, present in many commercial tomato varieties like ‘MoneyMaker’ (**Figure 2c**) (Schornack et al. 2004). Like Xo1, it has been shown to recognize diverse TALEs, including avrBs4 from Xcv, avrHah1 from *X. gardneri*, and hax3 and hax4 from *X. campestris* pv. *armoraciae* (**Figure 2b**) (Kay et al. 2005, Schenstnyi et al. 2022, Schornack et al. 2003). It also shows a resistance response in tomato when avrBs3 is overexpressed via *Agrobacterium*-mediated transient expression (Schornack et al. 2004, Schornack et al. 2005). Bs4 also detects avrBs3 when both are overexpressed in *N. benthamiana* (Schornack et al. 2005). Additionally, Bs4 can detect TALEs without an AD and TALEs containing only 3.5 central repeats (Schornack et al. 2004). However, Bs4 and Xo1 are not sequence related and have different N-term signaling domains. In addition, tomato and rice are separated by the monocot and dicot divergence, estimated at 140-150 million years ago (Chaw et al. 2004). Therefore, Bs4 and Xo1 have likely convergently evolved to facilitate broad-spectrum resistance to TALEs.

Figure 2. TALE recognition by Bs4 in tomato and Xo1 in rice. (a) *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Xo) TALEs are delivered to the rice cell by the T3SS, localize to the nucleus, and are recognized by Xo1 likely inside the nucleus, triggering downstream signaling involving the transcription factor ERF101 (Yoshihisa et al. 2025), HR, and resistance. When truncated TALEs (truncTALEs) are present, Xo1 is suppressed, preventing resistance and causing disease. (b) *Xanthomonas* TALEs are delivered to the tomato cell by the T3SS and are recognized by Bs4 outside of the nucleus, leading to further signaling downstream with possible intermediary proteins EDS1 and SGT1 (Schornack et al. 2003). (c) Xo1 and Bs4 show differences in the N-terminal signaling domain and unique LRRs. Xo1 has a coiled-coil zinc finger BED (CC-BED) domain (Read et al. 2020), while Bs4 has a Toll/interleukin-1-receptor (TIR) domain (Schornack et al. 2004).

Mechanisms of TALE recognition by Xo1 and Bs4 are still unknown. My lab has shown that Xo1 activation and suppression appears to require nuclear localization of TALEs and truncTALEs, respectively. This is distinct from the TALE NLS-independent response of Bs4 but consistent with the difference in cellular localization between Xo1, a nuclear-localizing protein, and Bs4, which is cytoplasm-localizing (Ballvora et al. 2001, Schornack et al. 2004, Read et al. 2020). Noting the similarities and differences between these R proteins, I wanted to use what we knew about Xo1 to explore the mechanism of Bs4 TALE recognition. My lab has also shown that mutation of residues in the CRR outward-facing (spine) residues of TALEs allows TALEs to escape Xo1 resistance, implying that the CRR spine is recognized by Xo1. Virulence assays testing chimeric TALE-truncTALE mutants (chiTALEs) showed that interchanging the C-terminus was enough to convert a truncTALE to a TALE (triggering Xo1), and interchanging the N-terminal region was enough to convert a TALE to a truncTALE (suppressing Xo1). We also investigated TALEs with domain deletions (delTALEs), which provided further evidence that the N-terminus of a TALE is dispensable for recognition by Xo1 while the C-terminus is required. To contrast, little is known about the structure-function relationship in Bs4-dependent TALE recognition.

The similarities and differences in resistance mechanisms between Bs4 and Xo1 proteins can be used to understand, broadly, how a NLR might recognize a TALE. This understanding may be used as a foundation to overcome current limitations in TALE recognition, such as the suppression of Xo1 by truncTALEs. By performing a series of experiments in the tomato-Bs4 system parallel to that of in the rice-Xo1 system, I uncover more similarities and differences in their recognition mechanisms, finding where one R protein may overcome the limitations of the other with the eventual goal of engineering better TALE recognition and resistance. Under the null that Bs4 and Xo1 have the same recognition mechanism is true, my hypotheses are as follows: tomato plants expressing Bs4 will not show different patterns of HR and resistance compared to those observed with rice Xo1 when inoculated with different structural variants of TALEs; nuclear-excluded TALEs will not trigger Bs4 resistance and HR; truncTALEs will not trigger Bs4 resistance but co-inoculation of TALEs and truncTALEs will suppress Bs4 resistance. I address these hypotheses in the following experiments.

Materials and Methods

Plant material

Solanum lycopersicum cv. 'Moneymaker' seeds were sown in Cornell mix, transplanted once at 2 weeks old to 6" pots and used in experiments at 5 weeks old. The plants were fertilized on weekdays using 21-5-20 All Purpose fertilizer at 1:150 ppm N and 1:100 Dosatron Injector setting and watered with clear water (no fertilizer) on weekends. Watering was done as needed. Plants were grown in a greenhouse maintained at 72°C and received supplemental lighting from 6AM to 10PM. A hanging box fan was used to provide air circulation.

Bacterial culture, strains, and plasmids

Bacterial strains and plasmids used are listed in Table 1. *E. coli* was grown at 37°C in LB medium. *Xanthomonas* strains were grown at 28°C in GYE (Glucose, yeast extract, CaCO₃) medium. Bacteria were shaken at 120rpm in liquid media. Two independent transformants were tested for each expression vector. Tetracycline resistance was used as a selectable marker for all expression vectors.

Construction of plasmids

TALE domain deletions were generated through restriction digest of an entry vector clone containing full-length Tal1c-3xFLAG (pYS103) to fully remove sequences of the domains of interest. pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ CRR Δ C) (pXYG6) was generated by digesting pYS103 with *Stu*I/*Eco*RV and gel extraction of the backbone fragment and re-ligated with eBlocks ordered from IDT to replace sections of remaining domains using NEBuilder HiFi DNA Assembly (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA), then cloned into pKEB31 using a Gateway LR reaction (Invitrogen, Waltham, MA, USA). Other plasmids created for this study were generated in the same way, with different restriction digests; pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N) (pYS191) was generated from pYS103 digested with *Hpa*I/*Sma*I and pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N Δ CRR) (pXYG7) was generated from pYS103 digested with *Apa*I/*Bmg*BI. The simian virus 40 (SV40) NLS was used for C-terminus deletion constructs (Kalderon et al. 1984). The cAMP-dependent protein kinase inhibitor (cAMP-PKI) nuclear exclusion signal (NES) was used for cytoplasmically located TALEs and truncTALEs (Wen et al. 1995). The mCherry fluorescent protein gene was used as a negative control (Shaner et al. 2004).

Table 1. Bacterial strains and plasmids used in this study

Strains	Description	Source
<i>X. campestris</i>		
85-10	<i>pv. vesicatoria</i>	
85-10 mCherry	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-mCherry	This study
85-10 Tal1c	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c	This study
85-10 Tal2h	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal2h	This study
85-10 Tal1c(3.5CRR)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(2.5CRR)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(2.5CRR)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(1.5CRR)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(1.5CRR)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(Δ NLS+NES)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ NLS+NES)	This study
85-10 Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(Δ CRR Δ C)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ CRR Δ C)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(Δ C)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ C)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(Δ N Δ C)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N Δ C)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(Δ N)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N)	This study

85-10 Tal1c(Δ N Δ CRR)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N Δ CRR)	This study
85-10 Tal1c(3.5CRR[33P])	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[33P])	This study
85-10 Tal1c(3.5CRR[33A])	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[33A])	This study
85-10 Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31EA32Q])	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31EA32Q])	This study
85-10 Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31AD32A])	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31AD32A])	This study
85-10 Tal1c(33P)	85-10 derivative containing pKEB31-Tal1c(33P)	This study
Plasmids		
pKEB31	derivative of pDD62 with a Gateway destination vector cassette (Invitrogen) between the XbaI and BamHI sites; Tc ^r	Cermak et al. 2011
pKEB31-mCherry (pYH4)	pKEB31 containing mCherry fluorescent protein; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c (pYS110)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c gene of <i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i> BLS256, with C-terminal fusion with 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal2h (pYS117)	pKEB31 containing Tal2h gene of <i>X. oryzae</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i> BLS256, with C-terminal fusion with 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR) (pYS107)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c with CRR truncated to 3.5 repeats, with C-terminal fusion with 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-(2.5CRR) (pSPC06)	pKEB31 containing 2.5 repeat TAL effector gene from pSPC04; Tc ^r	Triplett et al. 2016
pKEB31-(1.5CRR) (pSPC05)	pKEB31 containing 1.5 repeat TAL effector gene from pSPC03; Tc ^r	Triplett et al. 2016
pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ NLS+NES) (pYS172)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c with deletions of NLS sequences and C-terminal fusion of cAPK-PKI NES and 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES) (pYS173)	pKEB31 containing Tal2h with deletions of NLS sequences and C-terminal fusion of cAPK-PKI NES and 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ CRR Δ C) (pXYG6)	pKEB31 containing the Tal1c N-terminal domain fused with SV40-NLS and 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	This study

pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ C) (pYS192)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c with deletion of the C-terminal domain, fused with SV40-NLS and 3xFLAG-tag; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N Δ C) (pYS266)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c CRR fused with the first 50aa of Tal1c at the N-terminus and the SV40-NLS and 3xFLAG-tag at the C-terminus; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N) (pYS191)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c with deletion of N-terminal domain, fused with the first 50aa of Tal1c at the N-terminus and 3xFLAG-tag at the C-terminus; Tc ^r	This study
pKEB31-Tal1c(Δ N Δ CRR) (pXYG7)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c C-terminal domain fused with the first 50aa of Tal1c at the N-terminus and 3xFLAG-tag at the C-terminus; Tc ^r	This study
pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[33P]) (pYS24)	pKEB31 containing 3.5 repeat Tal1c with residue 33 of each full repeat mutated to proline and 3xFLAG-tagged; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[33A]) (pYS108)	pKEB31 containing 3.5 repeat Tal1c with residue 33 of each full repeat mutated to alanine and 3xFLAG-tagged; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31EA32Q]) (pYS34)	pKEB31 containing 3.5 repeat Tal1c with residues 31 and 32 of each full repeat mutated to glutamic acid and glutamine, 3xFLAG-tagged; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(3.5CRR[Q31AD32A]) (pYS109)	pKEB31 containing 3.5 repeat Tal1c with residues 31 and 32 of each full repeat mutated to alanine, 3xFLAG-tagged; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab
pKEB31-Tal1c(33P) (pBOG45)	pKEB31 containing Tal1c with residue 33 of each full repeat mutated to proline and 3xFLAG-tagged; Tc ^r	Bogdanove lab

Leaf infiltration and HR assays

The third true leaf of the tomato plant was infiltrated 5 weeks after sowing. A needleless syringe was used on the abaxial side of the leaf to fully infiltrate an area delineated by marker after the leaf was pricked with a round-tipped wooden toothpick. Inoculum was prepared to an approximate concentration of OD600 = 0.2 for single strain inoculations or OD600 = 0.3 for co-inoculations. >4 spots were infiltrated per treatment per experiment. Experiments were repeated with at least three biological replicates. Plants were kept under constant light with mild air circulation for three days before leaves were collected and photographed to measure for HR. HR was measured qualitatively by observing dead and desiccated tissue in most of the inoculated tissue, associated with darkening of surrounding leaf veins. Dead tissue from damage to the leaf during inoculation and from death due to progression of disease was not measured as HR.

Protein immunoblotting

Bacterial strains for western blotting were streaked on GYE plates with the appropriate antibiotics 3-7 days before harvesting to liquid culture. Strains were grown overnight in Moka liquid media and harvested after ~16h, then diluted to approximately OD₆₀₀ = 0.25 and allowed to grow to log phase (OD₆₀₀ = 0.4-0.6). The equivalent of 25µL of OD₆₀₀ = 0.5 bacterial solution was harvested on ice, pelleted, and resuspended with 16µL of sterile double distilled water and mixed with 4µL 5x SDS-PAGE sample loading buffer. Samples were then boiled immediately at ~95°C for 5 minutes or frozen to -80°C and boiled later. All SDS-PAGE gels were run on BioRAD 4%-20% gradient gels at 100V in a BioRAD mini-PROTEAN gel runner for 37-40 minutes (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). The resulting gel was imaged, then transferred onto a membrane using the BioRAD Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System on the Mixed MW setting (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). Protein was incubated with a rabbit α-FLAG or α-TALE primary antibody (1:1200; v/v) and goat α-rabbit IgG HRP secondary antibody (1:2500; v/v) and developed with 8mL Clarity Western ECL substrate for 5 minutes.

Results

Bs4 recognizes the Xoc TALE Tal1c and CRR-truncated variants

Previously, it was unknown whether Xo1 and Bs4 have any shared recognition specificity. Tal1c is a TALE from *Xoc* recognized by Xo1 and is used in our lab as a control TALE for disease resistance (activation of Xo1) assays because it shows strong Xo1-dependent HR. Tal1c and avrBs4 (a TALE known to be recognized by Bs4) have a sequence similarity of 84% while avrBs4 and avrBs3, which is not recognized by Bs4 when expressed by *Xanthomonas*, have a sequence similarity of 96.6% (Schornack et al. 2004). Given the differences between Tal1c and avrBs4, I set out to determine whether Bs4 could recognize Tal1c and confer resistance to the *Xcv* strain 85-10 when expressing Tal1c, with the hypothesis that Bs4 would not be able to detect Tal1c and would not trigger HR. *Xcv* 85-10 has no native TALEs, which makes it ideal for use in Bs4 activation assays.

I tested strains of 85-10 transformed with constructs carrying either the mCherry fluorescent protein (Shaner et al. 2004) or full-length Tal1c by syringe inoculating into 'Moneymaker' leaves. Leaves were scored 3 days post inoculation (dpi) for the presence or absence of darkened and dead tissue in the inoculation area characteristic of HR and resistance. I found that 85-10 expressing Tal1c triggers strong HR when syringe inoculated into 'Moneymaker' leaves, while leaf sections inoculated with 85-10 mCherry did not show HR (**Figure 3a**).

By varying the ratio of mCherry- and Tal1c-expressing 85-10 during inoculation (and maintaining the overall bacterial concentration constant) we show that HR can be induced even with Tal1c-expressing 85-10 concentrations as low as OD₆₀₀ = 0.003. This demonstrates that Bs4 can trigger HR and resistance with even small concentrations of 85-10 Tal1c, showing a highly sensitive Tal1c-dependent response. Although I have not confirmed Bs4-dependence of the response, I demonstrate in the following results that this resistance response shares many similarities with known properties of Bs4.

Figure 3. HR on ‘Moneymaker’ from 85-10 carrying shortened CRR variants of the Tal1c TALE. (a) Leaf images of syringe inoculations taken 3 days post infiltration (dpi) on a light box. Tal1c with a full-length, 3.5 repeat-long, and 2.5 repeat-long CRR showed HR when inoculated at $OD_{600} = 0.2$. (b) Modified versions of TALE Tal1c used in the assay. The 3xFLAG-tag is represented by the circle.

Xo1 can recognize TALEs with at least 3.5 repeats in the CRR, but not with 1.5 or 2.5 repeats (Triplett et al. 2016). It has also been shown that Bs4 can recognize TALEs with as few as 3.5 repeats but requires more than 1 repeat (Schornack et al. 2004). However, TALEs with CRR lengths of 1.5 and 2.5 have not been tested on Bs4. Because full length Tal1c triggers Bs4, I wanted to compare CRR length requirements between Xo1 and Bs4. I hypothesized that Xo1 and Bs4 do not have any difference in mechanism, and that Bs4 cannot recognize Tal1c with fewer than 3.5 repeats.

I syringe inoculated ‘Moneymaker’ leaves with 85-10 transformed with Tal1c with 1.5, 2.5, and 3.5 repeat-long CRRs (**Figure 3b**) (Triplett et al. 2016). 85-10 expressing Tal1c with as few as 2.5 repeats triggered Bs4 resistance and HR (**Figure 3a**), with the 2.5 and 3.5 repeat constructs showing consistent strong cell death. There was no HR with Tal1c truncated to 1.5 repeats. This suggests that Bs4 requires, at a minimum, more than 1.5 repeats for recognition of a TALE, and provides further evidence to support the CRR as an important region in TALE-triggered Bs4 immunity.

Xo1 and Bs4 recognize different domain deletion variants of TALEs

To test the importance of different TALE domains in Bs4 resistance, I then probed the regions of a TALE required for recognition using domain deletion mutants. Mutant strains were generated for both Xo1 and Bs4 assays. TALE deletion mutants (delTALEs) consisted of all single- and double-domain combinations except for the CRR deletion, which is already known to be nonfunctional (Triplett et al. 2016, Schornack et al. 2004). DelTALEs without the N-terminus were complemented by the first 50 amino acids of Tal1c, which is known to contain a functional T3SS (Scheibner et al. 2017), and delTALEs without a C-terminus were complemented with an NLS.

85-10 strains carrying delTALEs were syringe inoculated into ‘Moneymaker’ and lesions were observed at 3 dpi. Tal1c Δ C-3xFLAG consistently showed HR, while Tal1c Δ N-3xFLAG inconsistently showed HR (**Figure 4a, S5**). The dispensability of the C-terminus when triggering Bs4 is consistent with the literature (Schornack et al. 2004), while the dispensability of the N-terminus is uncertain.

These results differ from the Xo1 activation assays, in which the TALE N-terminus was dispensable, while the C-terminus is required to trigger Xo1. However, for both Xo1 and Bs4, we show that the CRR alone is insufficient for recognition and resistance.

Interestingly, Western blots (**Figure 4b**) show the individual N- and C-terminal regions of Tal1c appear to be poorly expressed in the bacterium compared to deletion constructs that contained the CRR. The N- and C-terminal regions of a TALE are disordered regions (Mak et al. 2012) and may not be stable without structural support of the ordered CRR.

Figure 4. C-terminal deletions of TALEs consistently activate Bs4 resistance and HR, while N-terminal deletions and poorly expressed N- and C-terminus-only constructs do not. (a) Syringe inoculation of tomato ‘MoneyMaker’ leaves with Xcv 85-10 transformed with mCherry fluorescent protein or constructs containing domain deletions of Tal1c at concentration OD₆₀₀ = 0.2. Leaf images taken 3dpi on a light box. The T3S (grey square), NLS (black diamond), and 3xFLAG-tag (blue circle) are marked on the figure. (b) Western blots to confirm TALE expression in Xcv 85-10. All proteins were 3xFLAG-tagged.

TALE spine mutations that interfere with resistance in Xo1 do not affect Bs4 resistance

Experiments with Xo1 in rice have shown that outward-facing residues 31-32 in each central repeat (the TALE spine) are important in Xo1 resistance. In alanine mutants of spine residues (and in mutants that matched non-recognized TALEs), TALE activation of Xo1 resistance was reduced or eliminated. If Xo1 and Bs4 both detect TALEs via the spine region, then the same mutations would affect Bs4 resistance against Xcv in tomato.

To investigate the importance of the TALE spine in Bs4 detection, spine mutants were individually transformed into Xcv 85-10, including 3.5 CRR-length mutants Q31ED32Q and 33P, alanine mutants Q31AD32A and 33A, and a full-length 33P mutant. When syringe inoculated into ‘MoneyMaker’, all spine mutants produced HR, showing that Bs4 TALE detection is independent of the spine region (**Figure S3**).

Nuclear localization of TALEs is not required for Bs4 recognition

To investigate the importance of cytoplasmic localization of TALEs in Bs4 resistance, I test the effect of excluding a TALE from the plant nucleus. It is likely that Bs4 does not have the same requirement for nuclear localization as Xo1, given it is a cytoplasm-localized protein and has

previously been shown not to require the NLS for resistance (Schornack et al. 2004). Our lab has previously shown in unpublished data that Tal1c constructs with deletions of the NLS and addition of a C-terminal NES (cytoTALEs) prevent Xo1 activation. The same construct was transformed into Xcv 85-10 to test for the effect of nuclear exclusion on Bs4 activation.

Syringe inoculation of Xcv 85-10 Tal1c(Δ NLS+NES) into 'Moneymaker' showed consistent HR (**Figure S4**), suggesting that Bs4 does not require nuclear localization to recognize TALEs and trigger a resistant response.

TruncTALEs do not activate or suppress Bs4 resistance

TruncTALEs, when expressed in strains of Xoc containing TALEs but no functional truncTALEs, suppress Xo1 resistance (Read et al. 2016). Little is known about the mechanism for truncTALE suppression of Xo1 resistance, and it is unknown whether truncTALEs suppress Bs4. To test whether truncTALEs can suppress Bs4 immunity, I tested for truncTALE suppression of Bs4 using co-inoculation experiments. From results thus far we see that there are key differences in Bs4 and Xo1 mechanisms of TALE recognition.

I transformed the model truncTALE Tal2h from Xoc BLS256 into Xcv 85-10. Tal2h did not trigger Bs4, as syringe inoculation of 85-10 Tal2h into 'Moneymaker' did not show HR (**Figure S1**). To test for suppression by a truncTALE in the presence of a TALE, I combined 85-10 expressing Tal2h and Tal1c in ratios ranging from a Tal1c concentration of $OD_{600} = 0.15$ to $OD_{600} = 0.003$, for a total bacterial $OD_{600} = 0.3$. Spots inoculated with any proportion of Tal1c showed HR and resistance (**Figure S6**).

A truncTALE may not be able to suppress cytoplasmic Bs4 with as much efficacy as nuclear Xo1, due to the differing localization. I transformed a cytoplasmically localized version of Tal2h (cytoTal2h) into 85-10 and repeated the suppression assay, co-inoculating with Tal1c. All ratios of cytoTal2h and Tal1c showed HR (**Figure S7**), demonstrating that cytoTal2h is ineffective in suppressing Bs4 activity when co-inoculated with Tal1c.

Discussion

The rice NLR Xo1 recognizes TALEs with broad DNA-binding specificities, conferring resistance to multiple strains of Xoc, which causes bacterial streak in rice (Triplett et al. 2016). The tomato NLR Bs4 has a similar TALE recognition functionality, conferring resistance to bacterial spot caused by Xcv (Ballvora et al. 2001, Kay et al. 2005). Here I provide evidence that these two proteins have unique mechanisms of TALE recognition, each with different limitations.

Virulence assays of TALE CRR truncations showed that 2.5 CRR units were sufficient to activate Bs4 as opposed to the 3.5 units required for Xo1 activation, though 1.5 units are insufficient. Virulence assays testing TALE domain deletions showed that the TALE C-terminus was expendable for triggering Bs4, while TALE C- but not N-termini are required to trigger Xo1. These results suggest a model for Bs4 immunity where Bs4 detects the N-terminal "half" of the TALE, for which the first 50 amino acids of the N-terminus or 1.5 repeats of the CRR are not sufficient. All other parts of the TALE are dispensable, including the NLS and AD. Virulence assays also show that truncTALEs did not trigger Bs4 resistance. Given that the C-terminus of a TALE is dispensable for triggering Bs4, differences in the CRR or N-terminus may underly truncTALE escape from Bs4 detection. The 44 and 14aa truncations in the truncTALE N-terminus may contain residues or regions necessary for

recognition by Bs4. These truncations were also proposed to affect DNA binding (Read et al. 2016), but our cytoTALE results showed that nuclear localization (and therefore DNA binding) of TALEs was not required for Bs4 activation. While it is also possible that the 28aa repeats unique to truncTALEs may deter Bs4 activation, the first 16 repeats of Tal2h are of normal length (Read et al. 2016). If Bs4 is sufficiently activated by the first 2.5 repeats, the 28aa atypical repeats may not have an effect. However, the full-length truncTALE CRR may still play a role in detection interactions as an element in a complex association mechanism, in which the atypical repeats may still be involved in the Bs4 detection mechanism.

We also found that Bs4 and Xo1 likely have shared recognition specificity of the Xoc TALE Tal1c. This result is predicated on the Bs4-dependence of Tal1c recognition in 'Moneymaker', which warrants further investigation using knockout or near-isogenic bs4 lines. It is curious that, when delivered by Xcv 85-10, Bs4 recognizes Tal1c over avrBs3, which has a much higher sequence similarity to the model avrBs4 (Schenstnyi et al. 2022). However, avrBs3 has only been shown not to trigger HR when delivered by 85-10 in the context of pDSK602 (Schenstnyi et al. 2022, Schornack et al. 2004) and has not yet been observed in a pKEB31 context. It has been observed that avrBs3 triggers HR when it is transiently overexpressed (Schornack et al. 2005). When delivered by Xcv 85-10 in the high-expression pKEB31 plasmid, Tal1c may reach high enough concentrations to overcome weak recognition affinity. Bs4 may also be able to detect other TALEs from Xoc, which may provide greater insight into which TALE regions are important for activating Bs4.

Additionally, while the CRR is required for Bs4 recognition, the identity of the spine residues do not appear to be important for recognition. Other residues on the TALE CRR may be more important for detection by Bs4; alternatively, the sequences on the N-terminus may play a more important role in recognition. Mutations in the TALE and truncTALE spine have been shown to impact Xo1 detection and suppression, supporting the direct interaction recognition/suppression model; additionally, co-immunoprecipitation assays have been used to show that Xo1 and truncTALEs interact directly (Read et al. 2016). Currently, there is not strong evidence for or against a direct-interaction model for Bs4 recognition of TALEs. Bs4 has not been shown to associate with the TALE avrBs4 in a yeast-2-hybrid assay (Schornack et al. 2004), but may still interact directly when in the presence of other proteins in complex. Based on my data, I suggest a model where Bs4 mainly recognizes a TALE non-spine region and truncTALEs neither suppress nor activate Bs4 because parts of the N-terminus that are required for Bs4 activation are absent (**Figure 5**). This differs from the current model for the Xo1 activation/suppression mechanism.

Figure 5. A model for Bs4 activation by TALEs that depends on Bs4 association with the N-terminus and first 1.5-2.5 repeats of the TALE. (a) The NLR Bs4 in the inactive formation. Most NLRs undergo a change in conformation upon ligand binding (Contreras et al. 2023). (b) Bs4 may recognize parts of the TALE N-terminus and the first 2.5 CRR units. Increasing TALE concentration overcomes weak recognition affinity (Schornack et al. 2005). (c) Bs4 requires more than 1.5 units of the CRR for resistance. (d) Deletions in the truncTALE N-terminus disrupt Bs4 detection. (e) The CRR may play a structural role in binding to Bs4 as an "anchor", for which the CRR spine is not important. Once Bs4 is bound in the active conformation, it may stabilize in a complex with other Bs4-TALE units and potential interactors to trigger downstream signaling and HR.

It is also possible that co-inoculation of separate strains of *Xcv* 85-10 carrying TALEs and truncTALEs is not sufficient for resistance suppression. It is unknown whether co-inoculation of *Xanthomonas* in rice can suppress Xo1. Previously, virulence assays of Xo1 suppression have been performed with co-expression constructs generated by transforming truncTALEs into the *Xoc* strain CFBP7331, which natively triggers Xo1 resistance (Read et al. 2016). Attempting to replicate these truncTALE-Xo1 suppression assays in tomato failed, as we were unable to confirm that the *Xcv* 82-8 culture used contained TALEs recognized by Bs4 in our 'Moneymaker'.

Table 2. Functional comparison of the R proteins Xo1 and Bs4.

Function	Xo1	Bs4	Source
TALE recognition			
Tal1c	R	R	Triplett et al. 2016, this study
avrBs3	No R	R at high titer	Triplett et al. 2016, Schornack et al. 2005
avrBs4	Unknown	R	Ballvora et al. 2001
Tal1c(3.5CRR)	R	R	Triplett 2016, this study
Tal1c(2.5CRR)	No R	R	Triplett 2016, this study
Tal1c(1.5CRR)	No R	No R	Triplett et al. 2016, this study
Tal1c(Δ NLS+NES)	No R	R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal2h	No R	No R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES)	No R	No R	Bogdanove lab, this study

Tal1c spine mutants	Some R	R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal1c(Δ CRR Δ C)	No R	No R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal1c(Δ C)	No R	R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal1c(Δ N Δ C)	No R	No R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal1c(Δ N)	R	Some R	Bogdanove lab, this study
Tal1c(Δ N Δ CRR)	No R	No R	Bogdanove lab, this study
truncTALE suppression			
Tal2h	No R	R	Read 2016, this study
Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES)	R	R	Bogdanove lab, this study

Comparing Xo1 and Bs4 (Table 2), we see that they have divergent TALE recognition specificities. Both cannot recognize and trigger defense against several TALEs, a similar weakness in their recognition capability. However, studying Bs4 may provide insight into the possibility of overcoming suppression by truncTALEs, a major weakness of Xo1. This study defines a Bs4 mechanism for broad recognition of TALEs, different from Xo1, that appears to be unaffected by truncTALE suppression, amino acid polymorphisms in the spine region, and nuclear localization. Separate mechanisms of TALE recognition regardless of DNA binding specificity provide the opportunity to explore ways to overcome limitations in resistance to *Xanthomonas* species. In addition, this study explores two NLRs of distantly related plant species that detect the same class of effectors with differing mechanisms and provides an interesting example of convergent evolution in plant immunity.

Future Directions

This exploratory study of the structure-function relationship of TALE recognition by Bs4 in comparison to Xo1 revealed new insight into how Bs4 detects TALEs. However, there remain many unknowns regarding the mechanism of resistance for both proteins — while progress has been made investigating TALE structure, regions in Xo1 and Bs4 important for recognition remain largely unexplored. Confirming Bs4-dependence of the 85-10 Tal1c resistance response can be achieved using susceptible *bs4/bs4* near isogenic lines (Ballvora 2001), which will not show HR when inoculated with 85-10 Tal1c if the resistance response is Bs4-dependent. Performing additional comparative experiments will reveal recognition requirements of both proteins. For example, Read et al. (2020) investigated the possibility of direct binding between Xo1, TALEs, and truncTALEs. Similarly, we could ask if Bs4 associates directly with TALEs during detection. Performing a similar experiment with Bs4 will provide more information on the possibility of direct binding between TALEs and Bs4. Screening chimeric TALE-truncTALE domain fusions can also reveal more about why Bs4 is unable to detect truncTALEs — which parts of a truncTALE make it unrecognizable by Bs4? Given the deletions in the truncTALE N-terminus, the amount of the N-terminus required for recognition is also now of interest. What parts of the TALE N-terminus are important for recognition, if the first 50aa are not sufficient? What parts of avrBs3 makes it a weaker activator of Bs4 compared to avrBs4 or Tal1c? Investigating the ways Bs4 functionally overcomes weaknesses of Xo1, as well as comparing both NLRs' recognition capability through further structural analysis can contribute to engineering broader and more robust resistance to *Xanthomonas*.

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. TALE and truncTALE activation of Bs4

Figure S2. TALE CRR deletion activation of Bs4

Figure S3. TALE CRR spine mutant activation of Bs4

Figure S4. cytoTALE and cytotruncTALE activation of Bs4

Figure S5. delTALE activation of Bs4

Figure S6. Co-inoculation of TALE and truncTALE does not suppress Bs4

Treatment	Representative leaf image (3dpi)	Number showing HR		
mCherry		0/6	0/6	0/5
Tal1c		6/6	6/6	4/5
Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES)		0/6	0/6	0/5
Tal2h(Δ NLS+NES) + Tal1c		6/6	6/6	5/5

Figure S7. Co-inoculation of TALE and cytotruncTALE does not suppress Bs4